

Hypersensitivity Of Gifted Students At Al Ain University

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the degree of hypersensitivity of gifted students at Al Ain University and how it differs regarding variables of gender (male, female) and class (fifth, seventh). The study sample comprised (62) male and female students. (30) male students (13 fifth grade and 17 seventh grade), and (32) female students (19 fifth grade and 13 Seventh grade). The study used the descriptive method through a questionnaire prepared by the two researchers to collect data. The findings showed that the degree of sensitivity of gifted students was average or high. The findings also showed that there was a difference with statistical function attributed to gifted students in favor of males and that there were no differences with statistical function attributed to class variable (fifth, seventh). The study came up with several recommendations

Introduction

Developed countries has recently realized that the gifted and distinguished students constitute one of the pillars of development that is why they paid great attention to them. Therefore, they created educational programs that fit and develop their potentials. The countries also looked into the qualities of the gifted problems, and the ways in which they were brought up. The countries also paid greater attention to the methods of caring for them educationally, psychologically, socially, and vocationally.

Like the developed countries which showed great interest in the gifted and distinguished, Arab countries also paid greater attention to this group of people as seen in the numerous programs created for them and demonstrated in Arab Strategy for talent and creativity 2009 (Sroor, Al-uweidi, 2013).

In the United Arab Emirates, teaching the gifted is one of the foremost priorities, though such a kind of teaching is relatively new in the Emirates. Despite this, a need for programs for the gifted in the Emirates is essential.

The national plan of sponsoring the talented might be considered an ideal framework for programs planning and implementing in the coming five years. The national plan for sponsoring the talented in the country was based on the most recent practices in teaching the talented. It might be a referral framework that orchestrates all practices and efforts to reinforce and sponsor the talented (National plan for Sponsoring the talented, 2018).

Several problems related to the talents of the gifted might lead the most threatening issue their feelings such as frustration, social alienation and extreme fear. The researchers will tackle in what follows some emotional and social problems from which the talented suffer and might eventually lead to their disappointment, ability regression, or talent perish. Thus, such problems have to be identified in order to assist in understanding the talented and the way of offering suitable help to them (Maureen Neihart, 2002).

Gifted children are one of the groups that are more susceptible to psychological and social problems. Such problems and challenges start the minute the talent is discovered in children or adults. Therefore, the need to determine such social and emotional problems become urgent and important (Renzulli, 1991). Several studies on education unravelled terrible scientific facts caused by neglecting such talented. Al-Suroor study (2001) pointed out that 20% of such students suffer from psychological and emotional problems.

Literature on education has been concerned with these problems. Jarwan (2013) sorted out problems of the talented into three categories: cognitive, Vocational, and emotional from which hypersensitivity emerged. In general, talented students show hypersensitivity toward family, school, and social environment. They very often show sorrow or joy in situation which sound normal to ordinary students. Most of the talented react in a very severe emotional way in response to situations to which they are exposed. Consequently, they suffer from problems in school, home, and with colleagues. Feeling just that they are different arouses in them doubts about their being right, especially when the behaviour goes beyond norms for it might be interpreted as delinquent or unreasonable. The stronger and more sensitive emotions of the talented person are, the more sneering the colleagues and teachers will be (Jarwan, 2007).

1.1 Problems of the Gifted Students:

The talented face several problems linked to them and to their talents which in many circumstances lead to the most threatening feeling which is frustration, social isolation, and great fear. In what follows the researchers

will tackle some of the emotional and social problems the talented suffer from and might lead to frustration, ability regression or perishing of their talent. Thus, determining such problems is necessary for us to understand the talented in order to provide the help at need. (Maureen Neihart, 2002).

The problem is defined as any unwanted result that needs modification; it represents a state of tension and dissatisfaction resulting from some obstacles that hinder achieving aspired goals. The problem becomes apparent when the individual can't achieve the aspired goals of his various activities (Al-Hareeri & Zahra, 2009).

1.2 The Most Significant Problems:

1.2.1 Hypersensitivity:

The gifted student suffers from self-criticism; he is a keen observer of his deeds and behavior. He psychologically suffers when he commits mistakes and always bears the burden of mistakes done by others. Sometimes the talented might feel to be unjustly treated by the society. Worse than that, they feel that the society ignores them exposing them to a high level of disappointment (Maureen Neihart, 2002). Which reflects one of the most apparent aspects which reflects behavioral hyper-sensitivity is the emotional development of the talented and the distinguished. Satisfying the emotional needs such as: withdrawing from a certain situation, showing respect for others' feelings, fear from the unknown, anxiety and depression, sinful feeling, self-punishment, and feeling of inefficiency, are essential for the guidance of the talented and distinguished. This is an important process for the sound emotional development which help prevent emotional problems from affecting their talent (Al-Iqbali, 2018).

1.2.2 Idealism and Search for Perfection:

The quality of perfection for the talented is similar to the erection of a multi-dimensional building. This quality of perfection is composed of compound ideas and behaviors associated with the high expectations the talented students expects from himself and from others. The search for perfection leads to misadaptability of the talented who put for themselves sublime norms and expectations that don't match with their capabilities to achieve such high levels. They always wish to achieve the perfect and distinguished which creates for them cases of anxiety that mostly lead to frustration (Gross, 2000).

The search for perfection maybe considered a type of behavior represented through a reckless search to achieve the impossible. Here, the talented measure their identity value by what they achieve. Their search for distinction might be viewed as a tool for self-punishment which leads to grievous consequences, being one of the most serious factors leading to frustration (Al-Lala, 2013).

1.2.3 High Expectations:

Parents of the talented always expect their sons to excel in several fields of achievement. Such a thing perplexes the talented and hinders their development. In addition, the pressures enforced by the family lead to other pressures resulting from the feeling of the talented that they couldn't meet their parents' requirements of high performance. This, in turn, leads to an exaggerated feeling of failure, in addition to a negative evaluation of their achievements.

1.2.4 Social Isolation:

Social isolation of the talented is often associated with those sufferings from gloomy moods mostly lead to frustration levels of social isolation. These are usually higher with those enjoying high levels of talent, as classified by Hollingroth who determined intelligence average to be more than 160. The gifted are exposed to several social problems, the most significant of which is social isolation, specifically when such gifted were exposed to acceleration programs for ages between 4-9 (Gross, 2000).

What preceded emphasizes the importance of meeting the psychological and social needs of the gifted. These can be achieved through educational programs, in addition to ones for guidance to meet such needs. Eventually, they will be protected from the problems to which they might be exposed. There are programs which proved to be effective (programs for: teaching thinking, Self-development, communication skills, and ones for leadership, etc.). All these support development of personality of the gifted. They also help them to socially adapt themselves to others side by side with academic programs.

All the previously mentioned programs qualify the talented person to be an active member in the society, self-satisfied, and live in harmony with the world around him. Thus, the support that the gifted student receives from the surrounding environment (his family) or the outside (the school) help him to play an active role in reducing intensity of frustration to which he has been exposed and help him as well in adaptation. Therefore, educators and researchers must take serious and constant steps to reinforce relation between family and school. This secures support for the talented in different contexts that fulfill their emotional and social needs. They also qualify them to proceed toward success and achievement.

1.3 Problem of the Study

The concern with the gifted and distinguished increases day by day as they are one kind of human wealth. The increasing need to discover this group, take care of it, guide it in order to develop their abilities and benefit their societies (Jarwan, 2013). Psychological studies reveal that the gifted have certain qualities: physical, mental,

social or emotional. Undoubtedly, recognizing these qualities help the concerned to identify their talents and distinguish them from their peers. They also help in creating the suitable environment to develop their abilities (Zaitoun&Ellala, 2019). Like other societies, the Emirate society is rich with talented students. This required people in charge of educational process to put down programs that develop and consolidate their abilities and provide them with the best surfaces via programs executed throughout the school year. The researcher, being a supervisor, trainer and teacher of the gifted students, noted that through direct training and discussions aroused by them they were more sensitive and more emotional than ordinary students. Most of them react with excessive emotions against the stances they encounter.

To the knowledge of the two researchers, no such study that discussed the level of hypersensitivity of the gifted students in Ein City was conducted. Due to our belief that the talented should be given comprehensive services, we conducted this study. Thus the problem of the study lies in its attempt to determine the degree of hypersensitivity of the talented students in the fifth and seventh grade from the perspective of the students themselves by means of answering the following questions:

1.4 Questions of the Study:

1. What is the degree of hypersensitivity that the gifted students at Ein city have?
2. Are there differences with statistical significance at the function level ($\alpha \leq 0.5$) in the level of hypersensitivity for the gifted at Ein city attributed to gender variable (male, female)?
3. Are there differences with statistical significance at the function level ($\alpha \leq 0.5$) in the level of hypersensitivity for the gifted at Ein city attributed to class variable (fifth, Seventh)?

1.5 Objectives of the Study:

The objectives include the following:

- 1- To identify hypersensitivity of the gifted students at Ein city and whether the talented children actually have hypersensitivity and of what size is it?
- 2- To identify the difference of hypersensitivity between the talented with regard to class variable (fifth, seventh).
- 3- To identify the differences of hypersensitivity of the gifted at Ein with regard to the variable of gender (male, female).

1.6 Limitation of the Study:

- Time limitation: the study was conducted during the second semester 2019 – 2020.
- Space limitation: the study was confined to public and private schools at Ein City, UAE

1.7 Terminology of the Study:

- Gifted student: he is the one who is academically distinguished in school and scored 90% or above in more than four successive semesters, in addition to his teacher's attitude that the student is gifted.
- Hypersensitivity: it is the instigator of the talent characterized by a set of characteristics the foremost of which is sentimental participation extreme love or hatred, clinging to ideals, self-awareness, and enthusiasm in performing duties with full indulgence. It consists of five bases: (psychological, dynamic, sensational, mental, and imaginary). It is called excessive psychological excitement whose significance is seen in mental activation away from the customary (Dakhil, 2015). Procedure wise it is defined as the total degree the respondent gains through answering the paragraphs set to be measured.

2. Literature Review:

Al-Iqbali (2018) investigated the degree of hypersensitivity for the talented at Al-Laith governorate with regard to the variables of study level and gender. The study used the descriptive method via a questionnaire prepared by the researcher for collecting data. The sample comprised (120) of gifted students. The results showed that the degree of sensitivity for the gifted students rated average; they also showed that there were no differences with statistical significance pertaining hypersensitivity relevant to study level and gender.

The study of Hawwash (2012) aimed to determine, from the perspective of the gifted students, in Aqaba city, the level of problems they encounter. It also aimed to determine the influence of such problems on the variables of gender and age. The study comprised (107) male and female students of that city. The results showed that the syllabus was not challenging for the gifted students; the problems related to high expectations of the students came next, then problems of inadaptability to schools, and the problems related to fear of failure came last.

Zahloq (2001) in a field study investigated the status, problems, and needs of the gifted at Damascus university. The sample of the study comprised (311) male and female students: (155 gifted and 156 non-gifted). The results showed that there were differences related to specialization of science major and gender in favor of females. In addition, the results revealed a higher cultural, social, and economic levels for families of the gifted when compared to those of the non-gifted. The results also showed that the gifted were in need for special things the top of which was scientific achievement.

The study of Mansi (2003) aimed to determine the most important health problems from which students with high creative abilities at the intermediate level suffer. The sample comprised (500) male and female

students. The results showed that there were special problems related to the creative students (isolation, introversion, absent mindedness, uncommon and unacceptable ideas, feeling of frustration for failure, skepticism, perplexity, and mistrust).

Mahasni (2001) conducted a study on a sample consisting of (1499) male and female distinguished students-ten graders and first secondary-joining programs for the distinguished. The results showed that the most important needs and problems of the distinguished were: procrastination, and non-challenging courses. The findings also showed that there were differences with statistical function in the needs and problems between the distinguished students joining educational programs for the distinguished and the non-distinguished in seven fields and in the overall grade. The differences were in favor of the non-distinguished in seven fields: fear of failure, parents' inability to take decisions, and self-understanding. As for the search for perfection and the non-challenging courses, these were in favor of the distinguished.

Garland Study (1991) aimed at determining the emotional and behavioral problems of the gifted youngsters with high mental abilities. The results revealed that the scores of talented adolescents, according to measurements of emotional and behavioral problems, were good. They also showed that the gifted with high mental abilities had fewer problems than the gifted with average mental abilities.

2.1 Commentary on Literature Review:

It is clear that some of the previous studies were concerned with the behavioral emotional and social dimensions for distinguished students like those of only Galand, (1999) and Al-mansi (2003), while others like those of (Zahloq, 2001); Hawwash (2012); and (Al-Mahasneh, 2001) were concerned with the gifted. As for nature of the problems, results of most of those studies pointed out the various types of problems the gifted students encountered, but they all agreed that those gifted students were exposed to psychological pressures resulting from psychological, educational and social problems which they encountered.

3.0 Methods and Procedures:

3.1 Population of the Study:

The sample comprised all the gifted students in public and private schools, fifth and seventh graders at Ein in the UAE 2018 / 2019.

3.2 Sample of the Study:

The sample comprised (62) male and female students, fifth and seven graders; (32) five grade Students and (30) seven grade students. The sample was purposively selected in 2018 / 2019. The reason behind the purposive selection was the students' willingness to answer the questions in addition to the collaboration school management showed in implementation of the study. Table No. (1) Presents the distribution of study sample according to its variables

Classroom	Males	Females
Fifth Grade	13	19
Seventh Grade	17	13
Total	30	32

3.3 Study Instrument:

The two researchers prepared a special tool to measure hypersensitivity of the gifted students through identifying the problems they face and the problem of hypersensitivity in the theoretical literature and previous studies relevant to the study subject such as those of Ateeq (2018); Iqbal (2018), and Al-Lalla (2013) together with the help of specialists in the field. In its final shape the tool included (35) items.

The researchers used Likert scale to explain answers of the study sample as follows:

4.3 – 5 = Very high, 3.5 – 4.2 = High, 2.7 – 3.4 = average, 1.9 – 2.6 = weak, 1.0 – 1.8 = Very weak.

3.4 Validity of the Instrument:

Validity of the instrument was verified by seven judges who are specialized in special education, talent and excellence working at Al-Al Ain University for Science and technology, in addition to expertise from teachers and supervisors of the gifted. They were distributed as follows: (3) teaching staff members and experts from Al Ain University, (4) supervisors and teachers. They were asked for their opinions on the questionnaire to verify the suitability of the terms with regard to clarity, correction, language, and serving the purpose for which they were designed. The researcher took the recommendations in consideration with regard to deleting the following items: (10, 45, 35, 41, 32, 7) and integrating some other items (2,3), (15,16), (29, 30), (39,40). The scale ended up with (35) items. Some items were also modified syntactically by an editor.

3.5 Internal Validity of the Instrument:

This type of validity was calculated through correlation coefficients of item performance and total grade of the questionnaire as presented in table (2).

total	P	total	P	total	P	
.101	25	.267*	13	.354**	1	Pearson Correlation
.434		.036		.005		Sig. (2-tailed)
.151	26	.508**	14	.592**	2	Pearson Correlation
.243		.000		.000		Sig. (2-tailed)
.254*	27	.000	15	.136	3	Pearson Correlation
.046		1.000		.293		Sig. (2-tailed)
.134	28	.804**	16	-.307*	4	Pearson Correlation
.300		.000		.015		Sig. (2-tailed)
.447**	29	-.044	17	.695**	5	Pearson Correlation
.000		.736		.000		Sig. (2-tailed)
.001	30	.335**	18	.326**	6	Pearson Correlation
.996		.008		.010		Sig. (2-tailed)
.599**	31	.643**	19	.239	7	Pearson Correlation
.000		.000		.061		Sig. (2-tailed)
.730**	32	.531**	20	.601**	8	Pearson Correlation
.000		.000		.000		Sig. (2-tailed)
.479**	33	.182	21	.655**	9	Pearson Correlation
.000		.158		.000		Sig. (2-tailed)
.367**	34	.404**	22	.204	10	Pearson Correlation
.003		.001		.113		Sig. (2-tailed)
.010	35	.149	23	.127	11	Pearson Correlation
.938		.247		.325		Sig. (2-tailed)
		.594**	24	-.084	12	Pearson Correlation
		.000		.514		Sig. (2-tailed)

Table (3) reveals that most of the correlated coefficients had statistical function.

3.6 Instrument Reliability:

To verify the instrument reliability, the two researchers calculated reliability coefficients using two methods:

- The first method: the Cronbach alpha was used here to determine the uniformity of items which rated (0.82) acceptable for the purposes of applying the measurement to study members
- The second method: this was the method of applying and re-applying the questionnaire to an exploratory sample comprising (41) teachers and principles extraneous to the sample with a two – week time difference between the first and second application. Afterwards, Pearson correlation coefficient between the two applications was calculated. Pearson correlation coefficient rated (0.83) for the overall instrument, acceptable for the purpose of applying the measurement.

3.7 Study Variables:

3.7.1 Independent Variables

- Gender (male, female)

- Class (fifth, Seventh)

3.7.2 Dependent Variable

Hypersensitivity of the gifted students at Ein city expressed through arithmetic mean of sample assessments for items of the study instrument.

3.7.3 Statistical treatments

In answering the first question, arithmetic means and standard deviations were used for each item of the questionnaire, and (t) test was used for the second and third questions.

4.0 Results and Discussion

- Results of the first question: what is the degree of hypersensitivity of gifted students at Ein city?

In answering this question, answer averages and the number of frequent answers of examinees on terms of measurement, were analyzed. Table (3) illustrates performance averages of answers on items of measurement.

Paragraph	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
	1.00	5.00	2.5323	1.25081
	1.00	5.00	2.7097	1.20636
	1.00	5.00	2.0645	1.06926
	1.00	3.00	1.2258	.63812
	1.00	5.00	3.0968	1.62672
	1.00	5.00	2.3065	1.38598
	1.00	4.00	2.0968	1.16941
	1.00	5.00	2.6935	1.22258
	2.00	5.00	3.3871	.96419
	1.00	5.00	2.8226	1.03265
	1.00	5.00	3.7258	1.13324
	2.00	5.00	4.4355	.80207
	1.00	5.00	2.1774	1.09431
	2.00	5.00	3.1935	1.09901
	1.00	5.00	2.8871	1.30704
	2.00	5.00	3.3871	.96419
	1.00	4.00	2.7581	1.09672
	1.00	5.00	2.7581	1.12622
	1.00	5.00	2.6935	1.49960
	1.00	5.00	3.4839	1.39955
	1.00	5.00	3.2258	1.12234
	1.00	5.00	3.6290	1.32113
	1.00	5.00	3.0161	1.31189
	1.00	5.00	3.0484	1.50874
	1.00	5.00	3.2742	1.54887

	1.00	5.00	2.7581	1.37526
	1.00	5.00	3.1452	1.18525
	1.00	5.00	3.3065	1.18167
	1.00	5.00	2.4516	1.00290
	1.00	5.00	2.7419	1.12986
	1.00	5.00	3.0806	1.14946
	1.00	5.00	2.5323	1.45667
	1.00	5.00	2.7742	1.17932
	1.00	5.00	2.5484	.98642
	1.00	4.00	2.8871	.81190
Total	79.00	126.00	100.8548	14.07107

Table (3) reveals that students' answers to items of measurement were average or high, but none was low except item (4) whose mean was (1.2258) and the rest of items rated high. Such a thing indicates that hypersensitivity disseminated among the gifted fifth and seven graders at Ein. The low standards of deviation reflect homogeneity of students' answers. The results of arithmetic means of the measurement were as follows: (1 – 1.99) Low, (2 – 3.59) average, (3.6 – 5) high. The highest arithmetic mean was that of item numbers (11, 12, 22), in addition to the rest of items excluding item (4) whose arithmetic mean was average. This result agrees with the findings of the following studies: Al-Iqbali (2018), and Al-Mahasni (2001). Which assert that there is hypersensitivity higher than average.

The result of the first question complies with the theoretical literature which points out that dissemination of hypersensitivity rating average and high might be traced back to curricula, programs of training and guidance provided by schools at Ein to the gifted fifth and seventh graders which never consider or try to solve the hypersensitivity issue. This dissemination of hypersensitivity which rated average and high might be attributed to the interest that schools at Ein show in the process of teaching and learning through training courses offered to teachers and supervisors at the expense of other problems the gifted might be suffering from. Family bringing up might also play a significant role in this direction.

Results of the second question: Are there differences with statistical significance at the function level ($\alpha \leq 0.5$) of hypersensitivity for the gifted at Ein city attributed to gender variable (male, female)?

Arithmetic means of performance related to gender variable were calculated as seen in table (4).

Std. Error Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	N	Sex
2.30060	12.60090	107.9000	30	male
2.15058	12.16553	94.2500	32	female
				Total

Table (4) shows that there is a virtual difference related to gender variable. To determine whether the difference was with a statistical function, (t) test was done to check the difference between the means as presented in table (5).

t-test for Equality of Means							Equal variances assumed	Total
95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Std. Error Difference	Mean Difference	Sig. (2-tailed)	df	t		
Upper	Lower							
19.94218	7.35782	3.14562	13.65000	.000	60	4.339		

Table (5) shows that there is a difference with statistical significance of gender variable regarding the level of hypersensitivity in favor of the gifted. This result can be interpreted from the perspective of: the gifted male fifth and seventh graders have been given training and guidance programs more than females, periodic meetings with school administration male students have more than females, or because of the training guidance in school administration designed for male students who were given more practice than female. This result disagrees with the study of Iqbali (2018) which indicated that there were no differences with statistical significance for the degree of hypersensitivity attributed to gender.

Results of the third question:

Are there differences with statistical significance at the function level ($\alpha \leq 0.5$) of the degree of hypersensitivity for the gifted students at Ein, attributed to class variable (fifth, seventh)?

The means of class variables were calculated as presented in Table (6)

Std. Error Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	N	Grade	Total
1.99584	11.29016	97.8750	32	5	Total
2.94372	16.12341	104.0333	30	7	

The previous table shows that there is a virtual difference related to class variable. To determine whether the difference was with statistical function, (t) test was used to measure the difference between means as presented in table (7).

Table (7) (T) test to determine differences between means.

t-test for Equality of Means							Equal variances assumed	Total
95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Std. Error Difference	Mean Difference	Sig. (2-tailed)	df	t		
Upper	Lower							
.87641	-13.19307	3.51685	-6.15833	.085	60	-1.751		

Table (7) shows that there were no differences with statistical significance at the level of hypersensitivity of the gifted students attributed to class variable (fifth, seventh). This result complies with the results for Iqbali (2018), and Al-Ateeq (2010). It can be interpreted from the stance that the fifth and seventh graders were exposed to the same training programs for they belong to the same administrative and supervisory area.

5.0 Recommendations

- To care for the psychological health of the gifted through activating the role of the education supervisor in schools of the gifted and normal schools which provides programs for the gifted.
- To hold establishment workshops for teachers to tackle qualities of the gifted (social, psychological, and educational) so as to deal with them in a scientific and correct manner.
- To hold workshops for families of the gifted to tackle their qualities and ways of dealing and to interact with them in a positive manner to reinforce elements of might and to treat their weaknesses.
- To show concern with curricula given to the gifted and to provide database to enrich school topics to which the gifted resort to increase their knowledge of the subjects they need.

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